

16S Ribosomal Gene Sequencing, Phylogeny and Multidrug Resistance of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Isolated from Clinical Samples at a Tertiary Healthcare Facility in Nigeria

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Abstract

This work sequenced 16S ribosomal gene, determined phylogeny and multidrug resistance of *pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolated from clinical samples at a tertiary healthcare facility in Nigeria. A total of 184 clinical specimens were collected from patients and were characterized by standard methods of culturing and biochemical tests. One of the bacterial isolates was selected and subjected to molecular identification using 16S rRNA gene sequencing by Sanger method. *P. aeruginosa* was subjected to antibiotic sensitivity testing by Kirby Bauer disc diffusion technique. After culturing, 94 (51.08%) were positive for bacterial growth; out of 94 isolates of *P. aeruginosa*, 15 (15.96%) were from ear swabs, 14 (14.89%) from skin swabs, 20 (21.28%) from burn wound samples, 18 (19.15) from used cotton wool, 12 (12.76%) from catheter, and 4 (4.25% each) from urine and sputum. Also, this study recorded high prevalence rate of isolates among the female than male (63.83% and 36.17%, respectively), and the highest average (34%) of isolates were recorded among the age group 36-45 years and the lowest prevalence (5.22%) was recorded among the age group 15-25 years. The isolate demonstrated high resistance to beta-lactams (Ampicillin, Amoxicillin, Ampicillin, Cloxacillin, Augmentin and Ceftazidime). Results also revealed resistance to macrolide (Erythromycin) and sulphonamide (Septrin); and the organism was resistant to two aminoglycosides (Gentamycin and Amikacin) but sensitive to chloramphenicol. The quinolones (Ciprofloxacin, Levofloxacin and Norfloxacin) were very effective against the bacterium. There was statistically significant difference amongst the zones of inhibition at ($P \leq 0.05$) exhibited by the different antibiotics. The quinolones may therefore be considered as reserve drugs for the treatment of *P. aeruginosa* infections. To avoid resistance development, illicit use of antibiotics is not advised. Continued monitoring of antimicrobial resistance patterns in hospitals and community settings is imperative to provide effective therapeutic options.

More Information

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Introduction

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is a common encapsulated, Gram-negative, facultative aerobic, motile rod-shaped bacterium that can cause disease in plants and animals, including humans. *P. aeruginosa* is a species of considerable medical importance [2,5]. The organism is considered opportunistic pathogen, and serious infection often occurs during existing diseases or conditions, most notably cystic fibrosis and traumatic burns [29]. It generally affects the immunocompromised but can also infect the immunocompetent [34].

P. aeruginosa is widely distributed in nature, but has higher prevalence in hospital environment, as the wards encourages bacterial growth [39]. The characteristic features of *P. aeruginosa* isolates that allows its persistence in hospital is the ability to acquire resistance to variety of antibiotics, withstands physical conditions like temperature, high concentration of salts, disinfectants, and antiseptics [40].

P. aeruginosa typically infects the airway, urinary tract, burns, and wounds, and also causes other blood infections [36]. It is the most common cause of infections of burn injuries and of the outer ear (otitis externa), and is the most frequent colonizer of medical devices (e.g., catheters). *Pseudomonas* can be spread by equipment that gets contaminated and is not properly cleaned or on the hands of healthcare workers. *Pseudomonas* can, in rare circumstances, cause community-acquired pneumonia, as well as ventilator-associated pneumonia, being one of the most common agents isolated in several studies [14,15,16].

One in ten hospital-acquired infections is from *Pseudomonas*. Cystic fibrosis patients are also predisposed to *P. aeruginosa* infection of the lungs due to a functional loss in chloride ion movement across cell membranes as a result of a mutation. *P. aeruginosa* may also be a common cause of "hot-tub rash" (dermatitis or folliculitis), caused by lack of proper, periodic attention to water quality [15,17]. Since these bacteria thrive in moist environments, such as hot tubs and swimming pools, they can cause skin rash [2]. *Pseudomonas* is also a common cause of postoperative infection in radial keratotomy surgery patients. The organism is also associated with the skin lesion ecthyma gangrenosum [29]. *P. aeruginosa* is frequently associated with osteomyelitis involving puncture wounds of the foot, believed to result from direct inoculation with *P. aeruginosa* via the foam padding found in tennis shoes, with diabetic patients at a higher risk [41].

It is a multidrug-resistant pathogen recognized for its intrinsically advanced antibiotic resistance mechanisms [37]. *P. aeruginosa* is not extremely virulent in comparison with other major pathogenic bacterial

species such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pyogenes*. However, *P. aeruginosa* is capable of extensive colonization, and can aggregate into enduring biofilms, which enhances antimicrobial resistance [11]. This contributes to a higher mortality rate of infected patients, longer hospitalization, more severe illness, and higher costs of treatment. When more advanced antibiotic drug regimens are needed adverse effects may result [10].

According to previous empirical findings, *P. aeruginosa* has a non-clonal population structure [27]. It has been established that the diversity of *P. aeruginosa* clones in extant populations is mostly generated by a frequent recombination of strains [27,24]. This mechanism of undergoing recombination also significantly contributes to the continuous evolution of *P. aeruginosa* within the lungs of cystic fibrosis patients [10]. In spite the non-clonal population, it is feasible to distinguish endemic, epidemic, or even pandemic *P. aeruginosa* strains disseminating in hospitals [33,27,28]. Despite the intrinsic resistance to several antimicrobials, *P. aeruginosa* may acquire additional resistance mechanisms to all routinely used anti-pseudomonal drugs [44]. Multidrug resistance to antimicrobial agents of strains responsible for nosocomial outbreaks have been frequently noted by different authors in previous investigations [6,12,11]. This study was therefore aimed at sequencing 16S ribosomal gene, phylogenetic analysis, and multi-drug resistance of *P. aeruginosa* isolated from clinical samples at a tertiary healthcare facility in Calabar, Nigeria.

Materials And Methods

Patients

The study included 184 (138 clinical and 46 environmental) specimens that were taken at University of Calabar Teaching Hospital (UCTH), Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria during a period of four months (from May 2021 to September 2011). The clinical specimens were collected after obtaining Ethical Clearance from the Health Research Ethics Committee of the hospital. The patients' age ranged from 15-65 years and were divided according to gender.

Specimen collection

One hundred and eighty-four (184) clinical specimens were collected at different sites using sterile cotton swabs, small screw capped bottles, a firmly stopper tube, syringe, and a sealed capillary tube [25]. The specimens collected include urine (23), ear swabs (23), sputum (23), blood (23) and skin swabs (23) and burn wounds (23) while environmental samples from hospital including catheters (23) and used cotton wool (23) were also collected. Each swab was carefully taken from the site of infection and placed in tubes containing readymade media (transport media - nutrient broth) to

maintain the swab wet during transportation to laboratory.

Preliminary Identification of bacterial isolate

Specimens were inoculated on Blood Agar and MacConkey Agar and incubated aerobically at 37 °C for 24 hours for the isolation of *P. aeruginosa*. Non-lactose fermenting pale colonies from MacConkey and large flat dark greenish colonies from Blood Agar (after sub-culturing on nutrient agar) was further subjected to conventional biochemical tests [9].

Molecular identification of bacterial isolate

One of the bacterial isolates was selected and subjected to molecular identification using 16S rRNA gene sequencing by Sanger method [30,43].

Genomic DNA extraction procedure

Liquid cultures (1-3 mL) were centrifuged at 4600xg for 5 minutes. The resulting pellets were resuspended in 520 µl of TE buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl, 1 mM EDTA, pH 8.0). Fifteen microliters of 20% SDS and 3 µl of Proteinase K (20 mg/ml) were added. The mixture was incubated for 1 hour at 37 °C. After incubation, 5 M NaCl (100 µl) and 80 µl of a 10% CTAB solution in 0.7 M NaCl were added and mixed. The suspension was incubated for 10 min at 65 °C and kept on ice for 15 min. An equal volume of chloroform: isoamyl alcohol (24:1) was added, followed by incubation on ice for 5 min and centrifugation at 7200 x g for 20 min. The aqueous phase was transferred to a new tube, isopropanol (1:0.6) was added and DNA was precipitated at -20 °C for 16 h. DNA was collected by centrifugation at 7200 x g for 10 min, washed with 500 µl of 70% ethanol, air-dried at room temperature for approximately three hours. Pellets were resuspended in 50 µl of TE buffer and kept at 4°C [30,43].

Protocol for bacterial polymerase chain reaction (PCR)

• Primers

- Forward primer: 27f (5'-AGAGTTTGATCMTGGCTCAG-3')
- Reverse primer: 1525r (5'-AAGGAGGTGWTCARCC-3')

• Cocktail reaction

Ingredient	Volume (µl)
Sterile distilled H ₂ O	6.44
5 U /µl <i>Taq</i> Polymerase	0.06
25 mM MgCl ₂	0.75 (1.5 mM)
10 mM dNTPs	0.25 (250 µM)
10 pM forward primer	0.25 (1 µM)
10 pM reverse primer	0.25 (1 µM)
Template	2
Total volume	12.5

• PCR conditions

- 94°C for 2 mins
- 30 cycles of 94°C for 30 secs, 50°C for 60 secs and 72°C for 90 secs
- 72°C for 5 mins

- Store at 4°C

• Post PCR analyses

To make agarose gel, 1.5 g of agarose powder was added into 100 ml of 1X TAE Buffer. Heated in a microwave for 5 minutes. Cooled briefly and 5 µl of GR Green® solution was added. Mixed briefly and poured into a gel tank with well combs. The mixture was left to solidify, and PCR products was loaded into each well. Electrophoresis (Gel-Field) was performed at 100V for one hour. Gel was viewed under UV light and pictures were taken. Expected product size: 1,500 bp. Sequencing was done using purified amplicons. Fragments were sequenced using Nimagen, Brilliant Dye TM Terminator sequencing Kit V3.1 BRD3-100/1000 according to manufacturer's instructions. The nucleotide of the isolate was subjected to nucleotide BLAST analysis to reveal their percentage identity/similarities, accession number, highest query cover (%), E value, number of nucleotides and verification of amplification of polymerase chain reaction.

Construction of phylogenetic tree

Phylogenetic trees showing evolutionary relationship of identified bacterial isolate obtained from University of Calabar Teaching Hospital, Calabar was constructed using the methods described by [23,15,18,42]. The basic steps in phylogenetic analysis include:

1. Assemble and align a dataset

DNA sequence of interest (16S rRNA) was identified and data set consisting of other related sequences were assembled. DNA sequences of interest was retrieved using National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) basic local alignment search tool (BLAST). Multiple sequence alignment was created using sequences retrieved. This involved arranging a set of sequences in a matrix to identify regions of homology.

2. Build (estimate) phylogenetic trees from sequences using computational methods and Stochastic models

To build phylogenetic trees, statistical methods known as maximum parsimony and maximum likelihood were applied to determine the tree typology and calculate the branch lengths that best describes the phylogenetic relationships of the aligned sequences in a dataset.

Antibiotic disc diffusion method

The standardized antibiotic disc method was carried out [6]. The end point, measured in triplicate to the nearest millimeter was compared with zones of inhibition determined by [8]. Five (5) classes of antibiotics were used, and they include:

1. **Penicillin:** Ampicillin, (10µg), Cloxacillin, (10µg), Amoxicillin, Reflacin (10µg), Oxacillin (10µg) and Augmentin (30µg).
2. **Aminoglycosides:** Gentamycin, (30µg), Streptomycin, (30µg), Chloramphenicol, (30µg), Amikacin (10µg).

- 3. **Fluoroquinolones:** Ciprofloxacin, (20µg), Norfloxacin, Levofloxacin (30µg).
- 4. **Macrolides:** Erythromycin (10µg).
- 5. **Sulphonamide:** Septrin (30µg)
- 6. **Cephalosporin:** Ceftazidime (20µg).

Multidrug resistance was taken as resistance to one drug in three or more groups of antibiotics [9,8].

Data analysis

All experimental results were expressed as mean ± standard deviation for analysis performed in triplicates using Microsoft Excel 2013 version. Chi square tests were used for the statistical analysis of our results and p-values that were less than 0.05 were considered as significant.

Result

A total of 184 clinical and environmental samples comprising of 23 samples each of urine, blood, ear swab, skin swab, sputum, burn wound, catheter and used cotton wool were collected to detect *P. aeruginosa*. Among the total samples cultured, 94 (51.08%) were positive for bacterial growth, while 90 (48.91%) showed no growth in cultures (Table 1).

Out of 94 isolates of *P. aeruginosa*, 15 (15.96%) were from ear swabs, 14 (14.89%) from skin swabs, 20 (21.28%) from burn wound samples, 18 (19.15) from used cotton wool, 12 (12.76%) from catheter, and 4 (4.25% each) from urine and sputum specimens. The prevalence of *P. aeruginosa* isolates among various clinical samples are clearly presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Prevalence of *P. aeruginosa* Isolates in Studied Clinical Samples

Sources of sample	Type of sample	Freq. of isolate	% Freq. of isolate
Clinical samples	Sputum (23)	4	4.25
	Blood (23)	7	7.45
	Ear swab (23)	15	15.96
	Urine (23)	4	4.25
	Burn wound (23)	20	21.28
	Skin swab (23)	14	14.89
Environmental sample	Used cotton wool (23)	18	19.15
	Catheter (23)	12	12.76
Total	184	94	100

Table 2 shows the prevalence rate of *P. aeruginosa* according to age group of patients and their gender. This study recorded high prevalence rate of isolates among the female than male (63.83% and 36.17%,

respectively), and the high average of isolates (34%) were recorded among the old group 36 to 45 years and the lowest prevalence (5.22%) was recorded among the age group 15-25 years old.

Table 2: The rate of *P. aeruginosa* Isolates According to Patients' Age Group and Gender

	No. of patients (n=184)	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> isolates in % (n=94)
Age group		
15-25	30	18 (19.14)
26-35	29	17 (18.08)
36-45	62	34 (36.17)
46-55	51	20 (21.28)
56-65	12	5 (5.22)
Gender of total patients		
Male	75	34 (36.17)
Female	109	60 (63.83)
Total	184	94 (100)

Table 3: Preliminary Identification and Characteristics of *P. aeruginosa* Isolate

Test type	Test type	Characteristics
Colonial characters	Size	1-5µm long (blood agar)
	Type	Type
	Color	Grey to green (blood agar)
	Capsule	ve (non-capsulated)
Morphological characters	Motility	+ve (polar flagella)
	Shape	Rod
	Spore	non-spore forming

	Growth at 35-37°C	+ve
Physiological characters	Growth in 40% bile salt	+ve
	Growth in 5% CO ₂	-ve
	Growth in sheep blood	+ve
Biochemical characters	Gram staining	-ve
	Catalase	+ve
	Oxidase	+ve
	Oxidase	+ve
	Coagulase	-ve
	Haemolysis	+ve
	Nitrate reduction	+ve
	MR	-ve
	Urease	-ve
	VP	-ve

Note: VP: Voges Proskauer, MR: Methyl Red, +ve: Positive, -ve: Negative: mm: Millimetre, (β-haemolytic)

The colonial, morphological, physiological and biochemical characteristics of the bacterial isolates indicated that the colonies were 1-5µm long in length, irregular, non-capsulated, grey to green on blood agar plates. All isolates were Gram negative, rod, motile (with polar flagella), catalase and oxidase positive, methyl red negative, Voges-Proskauer and urease negative, reduced nitrate to nitrite and demonstrated beta-haemolysis. They did not grow in the presence of 5% CO₂, but grew in 40% bile salts, and at 35°C to 37°C (Table 3). Based on the morphological, physiological,

and biochemical characteristics, all the isolates were preliminarily identified as *P. aeruginosa*. From the organisms, 1 isolate was selected for further molecular identification and antibiotic susceptibility profiling. The 16S rRNA gene sequence data of the isolate exhibited 99.72% homology with *P. aeruginosa* strains obtained from database. The sequence of the isolate has been deposited to the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) GenBank with accession number: MZ802728 (Table 4 – Appendix 1).

Figure 1: Gel Image of Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) of *P. aeruginosa* Isolate

The Gel Image of polymerase chain reaction (PCR) of *P. aeruginosa* isolate is shown in Figure 1. Figure 2 represents the phylogenetic tree showing evolutionary relationship of *P. aeruginosa* isolate (in red) with other

strains obtained from the Genbank database. The bootstrap consensus tree inferred from 1000 replicates was taken to represent the evolutionary history of the taxa analyzed. Branches corresponding to partitions

reproduced in less than 50% bootstrap replicates are collapsed. The percentage of replicate trees in which the associated taxa clustered together in the bootstrap test (1000 replicates) are shown next to the branches. The analysis involved 15 nucleotide sequences. All ambiguous positions were removed for each sequence pair. There were a total of 1062 positions in the final dataset.

Antibiotics susceptibility profile of *P. aeruginosa* against 15 different types of antibiotics is represented in Table 5. The isolate demonstrated high resistance to

beta-lactams (Ampicillin, Amoxicillin, Ampicillin, Cloxacillin, Augmentin and Ceftazidime). The results also showed the organism was resistant to aminoglycosides (Gentamycin and Amikacin) but sensitive to chloramphenicol. The fluoroquinolones (Ciprofloxacin, Levofloxacin and Norfloxacin) were very effective against the bacterium. Results also showed resistance to macrolide (Erythromycin) and sulphonamide (Septrin). There was statistically significant difference amongst the zones of inhibition at ($P \leq 0.05$) exhibited by the different antibiotics.

Figure 2: Phylogenetic Tree Showing Evolutionary Relationship of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Obtained from UCTH – Nigeria (in red) with Other Strains Available in the GenBank Database

Table 5: Antibiotic Susceptibility of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Isolate

Antibiotic agents	Zones of inhibition (millimetre)
Ampicillin	13.66 ± 0.72 (R)
Amoxicillin	10.33 ± 0.20 (R)
Cloxacillin	12.66 ± 0.72 (R)
Oxacillin	19.00 ± 0.50 (S)
Augmentin	12.66 ± 0.98 (R)
Gentamycin	12.33 ± 0.72 (R)
Streptomycin	16.66 ± 0.72 (I)
Amikacin	11.66 ± 0.72 (R)
Chloramphenicol	20.33 ± 0.98 (S)
Ciprofloxacin	18.66 ± 0.72 (S)
Levofloxacin	22.66 ± 0.72 (S)
Norfloxacin	18.00 ± 0.5 (S)
Erythromycin	12.66 ± 0.72 (R)
Septrin	11.33 ± 0.20 (R)
Ceftazidime	12.66 ± 0.72 (R)

Note: Percentage resistance of *P. aeruginosa* to tested drugs is 60.00%. R = Resistance; I = Intermediate; S = Sensitive; % = Percentage; ± Standard Deviation.

Discussion

This study was aimed at the sequencing of 16S ribosomal gene, phylogenetic analysis, and multidrug resistance of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolated from clinical samples at a tertiary healthcare facility in Calabar, Nigeria. Results obtained in this study through colonial characteristics, microscopy, biochemical characterization, and molecular analysis using 16S rRNA gene sequencing, identified the bacterial isolate as *P. aeruginosa* (Tables 3 and 4, Plate 1). The phylogenetic tree showing the evolutionary relationship of the clinical bacterial isolate is presented in this study as a means of tracing this organism to its evolutionary ancestor (Figure 1).

P. aeruginosa is considered as a common isolated bacterium from clinical specimens that causes a significant challenge for treating both nosocomial and community-acquired infections. *P. aeruginosa* has also been implicated as a prominent cause of post-operative wound infection in Nigeria [19]. It is one of the most important opportunistic pathogens responsible for 10-15% of nosocomial infections worldwide [1]. Identification and screening for suitable and

convenient antibacterial agent to commence treatment is necessary in reducing morbidity, longer hospitalization, and healthcare cost implications [32]. In this investigation, from one hundred and eighty-four (184) clinical samples, ninety-four (94) *P. aeruginosa* isolates were preliminarily identified representing 51.08% prevalence rate. Similar rate 50.3% was recorded in India by [21], 57.85% by [13] recorded in Iraq. In comparison, lower rate 32.1% was recorded in Gujarat by [35], while very low prevalence of 2.1% was reported in Northeastern Nigeria by [47]. The variation in *P. aeruginosa* prevalence rates in various empirical evaluations could be due to the type of clinical specimens, type of hospitals, studied population, geographical locations, and differences in hygienic practices.

It was observed in this study that high prevalence of *Pseudomonas* infections was found in the female patients more than males (63.83% and 36.17%, respectively). This agrees with studies conducted in the northern part of Nigeria [22,13,3]. This could be due to anatomical differences and urolithical mucosal adherence to mucopolysaccharide lining. In addition, the results showed that the highest rate of *P. aeruginosa* was 36.17% in patients (ages 36 to 45 years), while the lowest rate 5.22% was found among elderly age bracket (56-65). This may be related to the high production of β -lactamase via the genes of resistance and mutational processes [26,47,7].

In this study, *P. aeruginosa* isolate was resistant to ampicillin, amoxicillin, cloxacillin augmentin, gentamycin, amikacin, erythromycin, septrin (Trimethoprim-Sulfamethaxazole) and ceftazidime; with overall percentage resistance of 60.00%. Similar findings were reported by [1] in their study. The observed resistance rate in our study reflects the current antibiotic prescription pattern and the selective pressure that followed is that gentamicin and ampicillin have been much longer in circulation which will explain their relatively higher rates of resistance compared to quinolones with high susceptibility rate because they are relatively recent in hospital practice in this country. Our observation is slightly different from what [39] reported from Kathmandu, Nepal. In their study, *P. aeruginosa* exhibited high rates of resistance to gentamycin (57.1%) and ciprofloxacin (36.7%) among others. Gentamicin was introduced to the market in the '60s and this suggests a higher chance of exposure within the study population in comparison to the quinolones. The high probability of exposure to the drug in the hospital and the modification in bacterial enzymes are possible drivers for resistance [46]. There was statistically significant difference amongst the zones of inhibition at ($P \leq 0.05$) exhibited by the tested drugs.

Previous studies from Nigeria have indicated high rates of multidrug resistance in *P. aeruginosa* especially to penicillin derivatives, aminoglycosides, quinolones, and third generation cephalosporins. In a study by [20] on septicemia in high-risk newborns at a teaching hospital in Ile-Ife, Nigeria, *P. aeruginosa* accounted for 18.8% of the causative organisms with a high degree of *in vitro* antimicrobial resistance. An incidence of 19.6% MDR *P. aeruginosa* was reported by [31]. 18-31% resistance to penicillins, aminoglycosides, and quinolones was reported by [20]. From the foregoing, it can be unequivocally stated that *P. aeruginosa* has now emerged as a highly multidrug-resistant pathogen with concomitant high multiple antibiotic resistance index in this environment. This is also in addition to the natural ability of *P. aeruginosa* to resist penetration of most antibiotics due to the cell wall structure as well as its ease of spread in nosocomial settings [46].

Resistance to antibiotics of at least 3 different groups has been defined as multiple drug resistance [4]. Even though the multiple antibiotic resistance was not very high in this study when compared with those in some hospitals in other countries [29], the clinical isolate had relatively high multidrug resistance. Resistance to penicillin derivatives and other antibiotics (aminoglycosides, sulphonamide and macrolide) limits the choice of antimicrobials that can be used for the treatment of infections caused by this pathogen. These findings confirmed the multidrug resistance of *P. aeruginosa*. Several empirical investigations have reported the isolation of multidrug-resistant *P. aeruginosa* from diverse groups of patients and hospitals across the globe [14,18,32].

Conclusion

This study revealed the high prevalence of *P. aeruginosa* among common clinical specimens in the study area. Also, multidrug resistance of the pathogen was observed. However, the organism was susceptible to the quinolones (ciprofloxacin, levofloxacin and norfloxacin). These drugs may therefore be considered as reserve drugs for the treatment of *P. aeruginosa* infections. To avoid resistance development, illicit use of antibiotics is not advised. Continued monitoring of antimicrobial resistance patterns in hospitals and community settings is imperative to provide effective therapeutic options.

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Conflict of Interest

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Appendix 1

Table 4: Properties of Partial 16S Ribosomal RNA Sequences of *P. aeruginosa* Obtained at the UCTH Using nBLAST (GenBank)

Sample organism	Strain	Accession number	No of nucleotides	Highest nBLAST identity (%)	E value	Alignment score	Highest query coverage (%)
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	UCTH-04-CR	MZ802728	1,062	99.72	0.00	≥200	100

Note: n – nucleotide; BLAST – basic local alignment search tool; % - percentage.

